

Advantages and Importance of Cooperative Approach in Students

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Annotation:

This article highlights the benefits of teaching higher education students our ancient traditions and eternal values in combination with the achievements of modern science. Today, in the development of a culture of national dialogue on the basis of pedagogical cooperation, it is necessary to have a thorough knowledge of customs, traditions, national, universal, educational values, our national spiritual heritage. To do this, it is important that the teacher properly organizes communication with students and constantly learns to talk, to communicate. Because it allows the teacher to conduct the lesson effectively. Accordingly, the article scientifically analyzes the importance of the introduction of factors in the development of a culture of national communication in the educational process based on the effective use of methods such as conversation, lecture, storytelling.

Keywords: Student, value, youth, tradition, culture, communication, national, knowledge, upbringing, education, formation, development.

DISCUSSION

The education of harmonious, purposeful and energetic young people with modern knowledge and skills, able to take responsibility for the worthy future of the country, is the most important condition for the sustainable and progressive development of the country. In the years of independence, a wide range of works have been carried out in our country to educate young people spiritually mature and healthy, patriotic and selfless, to protect their rights and interests. In order to raise this sector to a high level of quality, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On increasing the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan” was adopted.

In 2017-2021, a number of new and important tasks related to the strategy of actions on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030, the concept of "continuous spiritual education" were set.

Chapter I, Section 1 of the concept of continuous spiritual education began with such words. "Uzbekistan has entered a new stage of development on the basis of the principle of" from the national revival-towards the National upsurge". The new era sets its own specific, strict requirements for the education and training system."(1.1.P)

Youth is a period of aspiration towards the future and goodness. And young people are the main force of society. Today Uzbekistan has become a country of opportunities for young people. There is no end to the conditions created for studying, acquiring knowledge, studying a profession. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev asked the question "What will you suffer from me? I will answer that the education and upbringing of our children, if you ask me, " is one more time that the need for the education and upbringing of educated teachers and students has increased in Uzbekistan. [10]

Today, the training of highly qualified, comprehensively developed, skilled, world-wide and deeply technical personnel is one of the most important issues in production. The modern university is a professionally educated, independent-thinking student, and also needs to realize the values of humanism both psychologically and technologically.

It is proved that the harmonization of our ancient traditions and immortal values with the achievements of modern science is one of the main obligations of modern scientific youth. For this purpose, in the development of the culture of national communication on the basis of pedagogical cooperation, we must perfectly know the traditions, traditions, national, universal, educational values, national spiritual norms. Because today students are required to develop a culture of national communication by creating cognitive skills qualifications in their minds.

Pedagogical communication is an indispensable attribute of pedagogical influence. This is a professional communication between the teacher and the student in the educational process, in which information is exchanged and educational influence is made on the students. In this case, two-way communication should occur. As its basis, mutual respect and trust serve In fact, collaborative learning educates the student on the daily intense mental labor, educates the mind, independence as an individual. It is envisaged to instill in each student a sense of personal dignity, to strengthen confidence in one's own strength and abilities, to form a sense of responsibility in studying.

The collaborative learning technology helps the student to work independently and painstakingly intelligently, to complete and qualitatively carry out teaching assignments, to fully master the instructional material, realizing that the success of the student in his / her education leads to the success of the group. (9. 77 P)

The correct Organization of pedagogical cooperation will be the basis for the development of national communication by studying the values in conjunction with the effective mastering of the teaching material in students. "It is natural that the national consciousness and its formation begins first of all from the era of national awakening, " says X. A. Musaev, - now awakening: according to the dictates of the period, the object of development is becoming a social reality. Because, people are formed and developed because of their worldview, vital conclusions, relations with each other, will and desire, national way of life, national painting, traditions and traditions. Therefore, national, lifestyle and culture are an extremely original form of expression of social reality."

"National recognition," one more scientist argued X.Polotov, -means the recognition of the socio-ethnic stability of people belonging to the nation".

As a result of the research conducted with the aim of knowing the attitude of students towards national self-awareness processes, the same thing has become known, many of them express the opinion that national self-awareness begins with the occurrence of each nation's own independent national state. People who have their own independence, national flag, national anthem, emblem and national Constitution are conscious. His knowledge of national affiliation, his love, his unlimited respect for language, culture, his understanding of his values, his good knowledge of customs, his knowledge of the past, present and future of his nation, his cohabitation with him are factors that show national consciousness [7. 26 P].

In the following years, on the basis of the great changes taking place in our country, the process of formation of national consciousness, the introduction of values into practical life has increased even more.

Values are a living history. Accordingly, the fact that young people study our educational, universal, national values and rich spiritual culture ensures the national identity of communication. The term value is a philosophical concept, as most people note in the literature, which serves to reveal the meaning of its activities committed by an individual.

Philosopher E.Yusupov said that value is a material, spiritual need and interest that satisfies that or that need of a person or society, serving their interests. In general, values are material and spiritual wealth, formed and developed in the process of the historical development of the life of society, affecting both the socio-political, economic and spiritual development of the past, present and future, absorbing into the minds of people and gaining social significance.

Hence, it is understood from the above opinion that value is one of the constituent elements of human life, expressing the importance of its material and spiritual factors in the process of social development by people.

“Values from the pedagogical point of view develop the consciousness and activity of a person, it is a cultural-educational tool that affects the formation of him as a whole as a person,” said [5. 6 P.].

Forms of manifestation of universal values have a relative feature, but it is also not right to understand this relativity as an absolute feature. In such an approach, it is possible to fall under the influence of a realistic view that “only relativity in the universe is the rule”. And in practice and in social activity it is possible to interpret universal values in a desirable way, to justify any actions. However, relativity in the practice of values has a certain limit. This limit is determined by the peculiarities of the object of value, its social status, natural-historical aspects.

These limits are also affected by the relationship that occurs between people in society, the needs, interests, aspirations, the demands, procedures, laws of life and life expectancy, etc. (sub-aspect) [3.114 P].

And by some authors this concept is interpreted as a set of the highest spiritual and moral qualities inherent in man. Location in the study conducted by Inomova, the interpretation of the concept of “value” is interpreted as follows: “when we say values, we understand the sum of such qualities as freedom, social justice, enlightenment, beauty, honesty, commitment to duty, which serve in the interests and purposes of the nation, Elat and social groups that are important to society”.

From our point of view, the first two of the above points of view fully express the essence of the concept of “value”. After all, as a value, not only moral, but also material factors are recognized.

In fact, it is necessary to understand that value is precisely in the formation of the spiritual and moral qualities of a person and that values of pedagogical significance are studied. One such value is educational value. "Educational values" is a complex of objects and sub-factors that give a person

scientific and theoretical knowledge, bring up high moral and moral qualities in it, have an important socio-pedagogical significance in his / her harmonious development, and also have a special significance.

Today, a renewed society develops on the basis of its spiritual, intellectual values, rich traditions of the people, Universal and national values, science, technology, achievements, as well as on the basis of restoration and development of spiritual and moral traditions.

Values and their use in the process of establishing social and pedagogical relations should be built on the basis of the content of education, its process and the organization of mutual relations in the "pedagogical - student" system. A solution to the problems of pedagogical relations is required. The pedagogical phenomenon associated with the training of the future teacher cannot be ignored either.

- respect for each other by the teacher and the student on the basis of values, traditions in the relationship;
- formation of aesthetic rich outlook, high spirituality, culturalism and creative thinking in students;
- it is an expression of its continuity with the history, folk habits and traditions of maintaining and enriching the culture of the peoples of Uzbekistan, recognition of education as an important tool of national development, respect for the history and culture of other peoples;
- teach to make socially significant decisions using forms, methods, and tools that allow creative thinking, prediction, alternative thinking;

It is necessary to determine the methodological, theoretical and practical basis for the solution of pedagogical, creative problems of the necessary level of training of teachers, first of all, in pedagogical higher educational institutions.

In his works written in the content of education, oriental thinkers emphasize the organization of the educational and educational process with the help of the following forms, methods and methods, guaranteeing the expected results (they are also important in the process of training and professional development of today's pedagogical personnel):

- describe the essence of conversation, events and events, explain by order, give information;
- question and answer method of teaching;
- Reasoning, logical reasoning, personal reasoning;
- monitor the process of social or natural phenomena and events, conduct experiments;
- Induction, deduction, algorithms input, analysis, synthesis, generalization; [5.84 P].

Proceeding from the above theories, we can say that it is important that every method and method used in obtaining knowledge has a conscious approach to the acquisition of education, regardless of what it is. Because it is known from the history of mankind that in every period of time people's consciousness and actions develop in accordance with this environment. So it is necessary to have enough intelligence intelligence to be educated today.

An educated person is a person who knows where to find what he does not know. G. Zimmel "in obtaining knowledge, the example is more useful than the rule." Isaac Newton (2.31 P).

It is known that humanity has such great opportunities in the section of consciousness, intelligence, that we are still unable to take full advantage of these opportunities. For example, judging by the definition of human science, intellektual is the most mature people use only 5-6 percent of their mental and active capabilities, which is the most important thing. Therefore, the period of paying attention to more people's self-esteem has come. So the most basic treasure is hidden in a person

himself. Man is a part of nature, and he is also a spiritual responsibility before the universe, nature, society.

The power and inexhaustible source of enthusiasm of this fountain is in the spirit of the trigger, the sharp mind, the mind in the spiritually rich soul of man. In young people, the formation of these spiritual-human qualities is carried out on the basis of a system of developing sciences on the basis of a complex approach, the harmony of amyology and theory.

The consciousness that motivates the spiritual and practical activity in the life of students and studens is knowledge. This means that knowledge is not the result of the process, but the fact that knowledge is the process itself, but it is necessary to motivate the person to continue this activity again and engage in new activities. [6. 96 P]

It is important to educate them in the spirit of respect for values and to formulate the idea and understanding of our spiritual culture, which reflects our nationality in communication on the basis of cooperation pedagogy. Because without speech, contemplation does not form. Young people who do not know their own history and customs and traditions will create the ground for the further development of such personnel tomorrow.

Spiritual culture has a living character in relation to material culture. Therefore, it is able to develop and operate independently. In this respect, spiritual culture plays a leading role in the development of culture and the development of society, and therefore performs managerial, directing functions. Every society, nation understands its own because of its spiritual culture, knows its needs and interests, its features and occupies its place in world history. Therefore, the development of a person's spiritual culture, spiritual consciousness is one of the most basic tasks facing society.

Spiritual culture also serves as a successor on all fronts between generations and the task of knowing the past. Thanks to spiritual culture, the culture of the past is mastered by the future generation.

Another important feature of spiritual culture is that it manages and harmonizes communication between people as well as between a person and the outside world. In this respect, categories such as behavior, culture of communication are important components of spiritual culture.

Today the concept of spiritual culture in the educational process is being understood in the course of the lesson to the students. The purpose of the project is to familiarize students with the modern achievements of pedagogical science, its initial sources and values, which are the basis of our national spiritual heritage, and on this basis to form their national outlook, to find a solution to their spiritual qualities.

Therefore, in the process of teaching pedagogical science, on the basis of the periodical demand, the student plays an important role in educating young people the spirit of tradition, tradition, value and respect for the legacy left by our great-grandfathers, which is our spiritual culture.

"The years of studentship correspond to the period of mature growth (17-23). During this period, a person is biologically harmonious, from the social point of view, he rises to the stage of maturity, physical vitality.

In this regard, we are referring to its development when we talk about the formation of the spiritual culture of the student's personality from now on.

It is necessary to take into account all the peculiarities of the educational process, the laws of the general formation of the student's personality, its changes in the higher educational institution in order to conduct pedagogical work in the higher educational institution, including the formation of the spiritual culture of students in universities. [8.30 P]

Farabi believes that the highest virtue that glorifies human dignity is “striving for perfection”, professional, hardworking.

And the Firdavsi states that a person has intelligence, consciousness, that he does not have crazy qualities in his higher qualities. In his opinion, contemplation is power, nobility, courage, self-esteem, purity is the glory of man.

The thinker, as at that time, divides values into good and bad characterizations; when honesty, justice, self-preservation, kindness, humility, grace, steadfastness, prudence, generosity, tenderness, knowledge, entrepreneurship introduce singaroos into good qualities, when one pursues, cannot see, hostility, the desire to make a fortune on the account of others and achieve a high rank, only thinking of himself, betrayal, infidelity, etc., enter into the bad characterizations of human values.

As can be seen from the above points of view, the issue of human values has taken an important place in the philosophical views of our scientists of the past. Due to the fact that the issue of human values is one of the core issues of human life, in each period it acquires its own relevance and becomes the object of research, the subject of debates. [4.16 P]

Our national values and spiritual heritage, which reflect our nationality, are conveyed through communication in the process of education of our culture. This process requires the proper organization of communication. Because communication is the basis of the formation thinking the development of information exchange.

This is the treatment of the individual's attitude so that with its help, people begin to communicate, interact and be influenced by each other morally, aesthetically, culturally, politically and spiritually. Therefore, treatment as a social category is directly or indirectly involved in the essence of its application in all spheres of life.

The process of treatment is of two-sided nature; it is in its essence more comprehensive than simply the transmission and reception of information or data, it is a complex system of interaction of two or more people. During the dialogue, the national traditions of what nationality people belong to are felt in the culture of colloquialism. [4.76 P]

Further improvement of these situations based on the above recommendations and discussions is significant.

- Establishment of activities aimed at increasing the national culture of young people in higher schools;
- Formation of skills of respect for national values in them, taking control over the work of each student-student according to the modern demand;
- Holding many events in educational institutions under the slogan “national values-our honor” and through this awareness of national identity in the minds of the reader's youth, formation of the national worldview;
- To closely familiarize young people with the Uzbek enlighteners and their immortal heritage, who contributed to the formation of our national spirituality, to promote their loyalty, loyalty, patriotism, supporting approaches in the realization of national identity in our practical life;
- Improving our national culture by enriching it with modern knowledge on the basis of modern knowledge.

Most of the young people who receive knowledge in higher education are potential parents, if they are young family owners. So, the existing national education in students who are increasing their knowledge in higher education is the ground for the strengthening of the foundation of tomorrow. Because, upbringing is like air. Even if you do not see it, you can feel the effect every second.

Today every age is necessary to work on its own and strive for modern knowledge. That is, it is important for him to grow his spirituality by taking modern knowledge and developing national modern education in himself, and to add his sense to the growth of the younger generation as a harmonious person on the basis of developed education.

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